

[Raphael Toledano](#) has entered the real estate world in 2009 during a time of economic crisis. Despite his lack of experience or knowledge, he was driven by ambition and determination to succeed. He had been working at Weissman Real Estate, a small firm from Lawrence, NY, which was focused only on residential rentals and sales.

After a year of hard work and sacrifice, Raphael Toledano was successful in real estate. He remained an extra year at the firm, and shared the profits with them- as an act of simple gratitude to Mark Weissman for the given opportunity. Success breeds success, and going out on his own gave him the opportunity to hire salespersons, bind deals together, and close more deals than ever before!

Raphael Toledano is [the founder and president of Brookhill Properties](#), a leading New York City real estate investment firm specializing in multi-family units and more. Founded in 2015, Toledano completed the significant acquisition of a \$97 million, 16-building multi-family portfolio in the East Village that same year. The deal included 301 residential units and 15 retail tenants.

Raphael Toledano's successful streak has not only earned him wealth and privilege - but it has also given him the opportunity to help others. In addition, he is currently involved in many philanthropic endeavors.

Raphael Toledano supports and maintains The Creative Little Garden- an oasis of tranquility in the East Village, in which guests can just sit down and relax. Unfortunately, there are homeless people living in the area as well. Raphael Toledano is a proud sponsor of food pantries and shelters within this area.